

End report 'Citizen Science (task 3.5)' of the ODISSEI Roadmap project

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1 Overview

The ODISSEI acronym stands for Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations. ODISSEI is made up of more than forty member organisations that financially contribute to its development. These member organisations include Social Science Faculties, Economics Faculties, Research Institutes, Public Research Agencies, Statistics Netherlands, and E-Infrastructure providers. The organisations in ODISSEI represent more than 5,000 social science researchers and ODISSEI aims to support their research by providing world class data infrastructure services that increase their access to data, computing tools, expertise, and financial resources.

Through ODISSEI, researchers have access to large-scale, longitudinal data collections as well as innovative and diverse new forms of data. These can be linked to administrative data at Statistics Netherlands (CBS). Combining data from a wide range of sources enables researchers to answer new, exciting, interdisciplinary research questions and to investigate existing questions in novel, new ways.

This is the end report of the task Citizen Science- task 3.5, which was executed as part of the [ODISSEI Roadmap project](#) (NWO grant number 184.035.014) between July 2020 and June 2022. The task leader was Peter Lugtig.. For more information, please contact info@odissei-data.nl.

2 Task highlights

2.1 Initial problem statement and goal

The idea of citizen science projects is that non-scientists (citizens) assist scientists in the collection of data. Commonly known examples of such citizen science projects are the Influenzanet project (<http://influenzanet.info/#page/info>), the Great Backyard Bird Count (<https://gbbc.birdcount.org/>) or Plastic Spotter project (<https://www.plasticspotter.nl>). The idea of these projects is that they all rely on volunteers to do observations of themselves (influenza) or their direct environment (birds or plastic pollution). Citizen science projects are often cost-efficient because of the use of volunteers, while volunteers have proven to be happy and able to record data over a long period (e.g. influenza self-monitoring). Citizen science projects can also scale up relatively easy and allow observations to be taken at scale (e.g. the great backyard bird count counted over 42 million birds in 2020).

Although citizen science projects differ from each other in many ways, what they have in common is that the data they provide are only useful when the observations of citizens are of high quality. Output-quality checks are much less common in citizen science. Output checks are however important too, because they allow the quality of citizen science projects to be documented, evaluated and improved.

Generally, data from citizen science projects can suffer from two broader types of errors that creep in during data collection: 1. Representation errors and 2. Measurement errors. In order to understand how both types of errors occur, and what to do about these errors, the Plastic Spotter project will be used to better understand why these two error sources are important, and how they can only be partly minimized by training.

The goal of the larger project of developing a Methodology for Citizen Science is to develop methods to understand output quality of citizen science data, and then use these findings to improve data collection methods by providing direct feedback to citizen science about the quality of their measurements. In the current project only the issue of representation errors will be tackled; other aspects are postponed given the reduced funding for ODISSEI.

What can be done to estimate representation error in geographically-linked data?

To overcome problems of representation in citizen science data it is necessary to first estimate the extent to which such errors occur. The focus of the project will be on developing a technical use case for assessing representation errors. The data from the plastic spotter project will be used as an example use case and show how one can improve the quality of the data resulting from such a citizen science project.

Use case: Assessing representation errors for the Plastic Spotter project

Some geographical data are publicly available. Both Google and Openstreetmaps provide databases that can be accessed with an API, and existing software packages (e.g. ARCGIS, Python, R) enable such linkages to be made. When the geolocation of a picture is sent to the API, one can collect details on the name of the waterway, nearby buildings and their functions and land use for example. Many of the

other data that are relevant for understanding representation errors are however not publicly accessible. In the context of the plastic pollution project, one can for example link to publicly available data on the infrastructure (e.g. number of waste baskets in the area, presence of fast-food restaurants, presence of boats in the canals) to understand how plastic pollution is distributed throughout the city. These data sources are available in different public data sources, need to be approached with different APIs, and use different standards. One part of the project is to outline what standards are there, and develop a tool that works across the main standards for coding geographical data.

Not all geographical data are publicly available. For example, in the context of the plastic spotter project, it is important to understand how intensely the different waterways are used and understand the flow directions and speeds of the different waterways. Data on the waterways are available through databases maintained by Rijkswaterstaat (www.waterinfo.rws.nl), while data on the intensity of traffic and use are available through Statistics Netherlands. These datasets are not publicly available and cannot be approached by an API.

Statistics Netherlands is one of the partners of the ODISSEI project. A dedicated server with detailed geographical information from public and private sources is already available for internal use at Statistics Netherlands to geographically enrich data. In this project data from the plastic spotter project will be linked to these databases with the goal of linking to one or more private data sources. In practice, the following steps are taken to achieve this goal:

1. Data from Rijkswaterstaat will be linked to this server
2. Data from the plastic spotter project collected within the city of Leiden will be linked to geographical data from Statistics Netherlands and Rijkswaterstaat

The results from this project will feed into a more detailed use case that can form the basis of a next round of grant applications to automate the geographic data enrichment

2.2 Intended deliverables at the end of the project

An example paper will be published online to explain the use case in some detail, but will not be an official deliverable of this project (working paper), CC-BY-4.0. The technical case will not be disseminated but will be used as input for a future ODISSEI grant. The R package that will be developed for the task will be disseminated via the ODISSEI GitHub repository.

2.3 Layman summary

Citizen science projects aim to involve ordinary citizens in the design, collection and analysis of scientific data. In the Netherlands, many different projects have been set up around citizen science, for example, to count birds or bees in the garden, to count and picture the extent of plastic pollution, or produce a database of marital documents.

Although citizen science projects can make a big impact for citizen scientists, and provide valuable data, citizen science data are underused by both social scientists and humanities researchers as well as policy makers. One of the reasons for this is that citizen science data are often very selective.

Observations are only made by volunteers, and many areas remain unobserved. Citizen science can be made more interesting by linking them to other data. This can often be done by geographical linkages. Hotspots of plastic pollution can then for example be understood by their surroundings (the built environment), traffic movements in the area, or the number and type of residents living in this area.

The work under this ODISSEI task produced software to make geographic linkages to data from OpenStreetmaps, which contains a lot of geographical context information, and produced an example paper showing how such linkages can be used to widen the use of citizen science data.

3 Task end report

3.1 Conclusions

Early in the project, the SODA data science team produced a software package that can be used to link and enrich citizen science data. This package was then tested on at least 5 different citizen science datasets, documented, and published on the Github page of the Social Data Science Team of ODISSEI.

In a second step the analysis of the use case around plastic pollution in Leiden was performed. Findings were shared with the researchers involved in the plastic spotter project. Because the dataset used here was relatively small, the team decided to write an example paper with a different citizen science dataset: the "Globe at Night" dataset, which is a worldwide project documenting the darkness of the night sky.

The example paper for our approach was finalized in August 2022, and is now published. Further dissemination of both the package 'osmenrich' and the example paper are foreseen at the ODISSEI conference in November 2022.

One part of the project that has been less successful is outlining the standards around geographical linkage that would be required to scale up geo-enrichment to also work with other packages such as Python, and to work within the wider ODISSEI project (notably with geo-information at Statistics Netherlands). Early work on this led to the conclusion that good enrichment procedures within ODISSEI would ideally follow FAIR standards, as these are widely adopted within ODISSEI. Because linking citizen science data in a FAIR way entails much more than just choosing one specific standard for linking geo-information, a decision was made to embed this work in a larger workpackage within the CLARIAH-ODISSEI project proposal for National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Infrastructure (Nationale Roadmap Grootchalige Wetenschappelijke Infrastructuur). The current project provided the input for this new project proposal, and should this project receive funding, a postdoc will have about three years of time to link and enrich citizen science data in a FAIR way. Should this proposal not receive funding, then new funding needs to be sought.

As part of the work on this task, there are now strong links between the task leader and Social Data Science Team to the National Action Plan Open Science: citizen science. It is likely that this National Action Plan will result in new funding for citizen science generally, and data curation and linkage more specifically.

3.2 Dissemination activities

Output:

During the project, *osmenrich* software was developed. The main goal of the package is to easily enrich geocoded data (latitude/longitude) with geographic features from OpenStreetMap (OSM). The main language of the package is R and this package is designed to work with the *sf* and *osmdata* packages for collecting and manipulating geodata. The code for the software developed in the project is published online: <https://github.com/sodascience/osmenrich>

An example paper was also published. In their paper Peter Lugtig (UU), Erik-Jan van Kesteren (UU) and Annemarie Timmers (UU) have addressed the problem of geospatial sampling bias in citizen science projects by enriching the volunteer-collected data with geographical covariates, and then using regression-based models to correct for bias. The authors have shown that night sky brightness estimates change substantially after correction, and that the corrected inferences better represent an external satellite-derived measure of skyglow. They conclude that geospatial bias correction can greatly increase the scientific value of citizen science projects. The paper is published as a preprint and is submitted to the journal "Citizen Science: theory and practice".

Peter Lugtig, Erik-Jan van Kesteren, Annemarie Timmers. *Correcting inferences for volunteer-collected data with geospatial sampling bias. Preprint:*
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.0413>

The team has also presented their work at the ODISSEI conferences of 2021 and 2022.